

DOI

ZROZUMIENIE ADMINISTRACJI PUBLICZNEJ NA UKRAINIE

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Streszczenie. W artykule naukowym autor bada etymologiczne rozumienie pojęć “administracja publiczna”, “zarządzanie krajem”, analizuje poglądy czołowych naukowców zajmujących się pojęciem administracji publicznej. Autor analizuje zapisy „Koncepcji reformy administracji publicznej na Ukrainie” i określa, że kompetencje urzędników publicznych są ograniczone do wykonywania funkcji organizacyjnych, administracyjnych i doradczych: “urzędnicy służby cywilnej to osoby zajmujące stanowiska administracyjne związane z wykonywaniem funkcji organizacyjno-administracyjno-doradczych”. W konkluzji autor proponuje, aby zakładać, że zarządzanie krajem i administracja publiczna są podtypy (komponenty) gospodarki społecznej. Administracja publiczna jest łącznikiem między administracją publiczną i zarządzaniem krajem oraz zapewnia organizację i realizację jego decyzji. Kluczowe elementy dla zarządzania krajem to państwo i władza państwowa, a dla administracji publicznej - społeczeństwo i władza publiczna. Autorytaryzm jest charakterystyczny dla zarządzania krajem, a demokracja jest charakterystyczna dla administracji publicznej. Administracja publiczna wprowadza demokratyczne wartości i przyczynia się do zrównoważonego rozwoju państwa Ukrainy w procesie transformacji społecznej.

Słowa kluczowe: prawo administracyjne, proces administracyjny, państwo, władza, administracja publiczna, administracja publiczna, zarządzanie krajem.

UNDERSTANDING OF THE PUBLIC ADMINISTRATING IN UKRAINE

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Abstract. The author explores etymological understanding of the terms of public administrating, public management, analyzes the views of leading scholars who have studied the issue of concept of public management and public administrating. The author analyzes the provisions of "The concept of reforming of public administration in Ukraine" and determines that the competence of public servants is limited to the performance of organizational and administrative, advisory and consultative functions: “the public servants are persons who hold administrative positions that are related to the

performance of organizational and administrative, advisory and consultative functions”. The author offers to consider that public management and public administrating are subtypes (components) of social management in the conclusions. Public administrating is the link between state management and public management and ensures the organization and implementation of its decisions. The key elements for state management are the state and state power, and for public administrating, are society and public power. The object is the state in state management, and the object is society in public administrating. Authoritarianism is characteristic of state management, and democracy is characteristic of public administrating. Public administrating introduces democratic values and contributes to the sustainable development of the state of Ukraine in the process of social transformation.

Keywords: administrative law, administrative process, state, power, public management, public administrating, state management

РОЗУМІННЯ ПУБЛІЧНОГО АДМІНІСТРУВАННЯ В УКРАЇНІ

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Анотація. У науковій статті автор досліджує етимологічне розуміння термінів публічне адміністрування, публічне управління, проводить аналіз поглядів провідних науковців які досліджували питання поняття публічного управління та публічного адміністрування. Автор аналізує положення “Концепції реформування публічної адміністрації в Україні” та визначає, що компетенція публічних службовців обмежується виконанням організаційно-розпорядчих та консультативно-дорадчих функцій: “публічними службовцями є особи, що обіймають адміністративні посади, пов’язані з виконанням організаційно-розпорядчих та консультативно-дорадчих функцій”. У висновках автор пропонує вважати, що державне управління та публічне адміністрування є підвидами (складовими) соціального управління. Публічне адміністрування є зв’язком між державним управлінням і публічним управлінням і забезпечує організацію та втілення його рішень. Ключовими елементами для державного управління є держава і державна влада, а для публічного адміністрування – суспільство та публічна влада. У державному управлінні об’єктом виступає держава, а в публічному адмініструванні об’єктом є суспільство. Для державного управління характерний авторитаризм, а для публічного адміністрування – демократія. Публічне адміністрування впроваджує демократичні цінності та сприяє сталому розвитку держави України в процесі суспільної трансформації.

Ключові слова: адміністративне право, адміністративний процес, держава, влада, публічне управління, публічне адміністрування, державну управління.

Relevance of the topic. The provisions of Article 5 of the Constitution of Ukraine stipulate that "the people exercise power directly and through state authorities and local self-government bodies" (*Constitution of Ukraine, 1996*). All power in Ukraine belongs to the people. The power of the people is primary, unified and inalienable, ie state authorities and local governments exercise power in Ukraine, which comes from the people. Democracy itself is the essence of the Ukrainian democratic state. In relations with the state authorities, the people act as an electoral corps, ie all citizens of Ukraine who have the right to vote. Through free elections, the people of Ukraine transfer to the state, represented by its organs, the power that belongs to it, and the latter exercises it on behalf of and with the participation of the people. Elections provide the initial legitimacy of state power, ie its compliance with social ideals. Subsequent identification is provided by periodically checking the compliance of public opinion with the results of state power.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Issues of public administration and transformation of this system were studied by such scientists as A. Averyanov, G. Atamanchuk, V. Bakumenko, V. Malinovsky, V. Martynenko, M. Minenko, P. Nadolishny, N. Nyzhnyk, O. Obolensky, S Stetsenko, Y. Surmin, Y. Sharov and others.

The works of scientists I. Hrytsiak, I. Koliushko, V. Kovalenko, A. Kolodiy, N. Meltyukhova are devoted to the study of public administration.

The relationship between public administration and public administration was studied by M. Lakhyzha, M. Minenko, and O. Svitlychny. However, the question of the relationship between the concepts of "public administration" and "public administration" remains insufficiently studied in domestic science.

The term "public management" was first used by the English civil servant Desmond Keeling in 1972. "Public administration is the search for the best way to use resources to achieve priority public policy goals" (*Keeling D., 1972, p. 15*).

The concept of "public" comes from the Latin word *publicus* - public, popular, public. Linguist-lexicologist and translator Julian Kobylyansky in his Latin-Ukrainian dictionary translates the word *publicus* as "people's, people's, public, state" (*Latin-Ukrainian dictionary for secondary schools, 1912*).

The "Dictionary of Foreign Words" defines the concept of "public" as open, public, public (*Dictionary of Foreign Words 1977, p. 560*). "New explanatory dictionary of the Ukrainian language" gives several meanings of the word "public":

1. Occurring in the presence of the public, people; public, public, public, open.
2. Designed for wide visiting, use; public, general, public.

3. Concerns the public (*New Explanatory Dictionary of the Ukrainian language, 2000, p. 843*).

Consider the components of the concept of "public administration". The dictionary of words of foreign origin states that "public" comes from Latin. "Public", "people's" and has the following definitions: 1. Which takes place in the presence of the public, people;

It is worth noting that the term "public administration" comes from English. "Public administration". In a narrow sense, public administration is related to the executive branch and is considered as:

- professional activity of civil servants, which includes all types of activities aimed at implementing government decisions (*Kupryashin G.L., 2003*);
- study, development and implementation of government policies;

- interdisciplinary academic field based on the theory and concepts of economics, political science, sociology, administrative law, management (*Public Administration Review, 1996*).

Well-known domestic scholar of public policy analysis Oleksandr Kiliievych translates the English word "public" into Ukrainian as "public, public, state" (*Kiliievych O. 2003*).

Thus, the people are the source of power. In other words, the people elect the government, delegating to it certain functions. The government performs such specific functions as: management, defense, social and economic. The government, represented by public authorities, implements these functions in the form of policy. Also, along with the delegation of certain functions, the people give power financial resources in the form of part of national income. Accordingly, all these specific state functions have the feature of publicity. That is, they are provided for the people (society). When we talk about public administration, we mean, accordingly, the administration in which the people participate.

Given the publicity of public administration and the influence of society on its actions, we can say that public administration is the interaction of public authorities with society in the form of implementation of specific public functions in order to ensure socio-political effect.

In Ukraine, the term "public administration" is used, which is not an exact reflection of the term "administration".

Many domestic scholars consider the concepts of "management" and "administration" to be equivalent.

The English word management cannot be unambiguously replaced as "management" or "administration".

Oxford Wordpower Dictionary (1998), which offers the following interpretations of administration, such as: 1) control or management of something (for example, systems, organization or business); 2) a group of people who organize or control something; 3) often the Administration (in the American interpretation) - the government of the country, especially the United States.

The Longman Exams Dictionary, published in Edinburgh in 2006, provides the following interpretation of "administration": 1) activities that combine the management of an enterprise or organization; 2) the government of the country in a special period of time; 3) the process of managing something, especially with regard to laws, certain government inspections.

It is worth agreeing with scholars who believe that the term "administration" is used mainly as an organizational and administrative method of public administration used by public authorities. In other words, administration is a bureaucratic method of governing society based on the power and authority of power, ie in orders, decrees, orders, instructions and instructions. This method is specific and is mainly used by the executive authorities in the person of civil servants. That is, in our opinion, public administration is implemented by public servants who work in public organizations and perform a wide range of tasks.

According to the "Concept of Public Administration Reform in Ukraine", the competence of public servants is limited to the performance of organizational and administrative and advisory functions: "public servants are persons who hold administrative positions related to the performance of organizational and administrative

and advisory functions” (*Public administration reform in Ukraine: draft concepts and laws, 2006*). This definition does not take into account control and supervisory and other management functions, as well as the provision of administrative and public services.

According to the UN glossary, public administration has many definitions. According to some authors, public administration is a centralized organization of government policies and programs, as well as coordination of staff activities. Other experts in the field of public administration determine that public administration is related to the implementation of laws and other norms adopted by the legislative bodies of the state. Others argue that public administration is used in managerial, political and legal theory and is a procedure for implementing legislative, executive and judicial branches of government to regulate and provide services to the public (*Glossary of the United Nations Public Administration Development Program*).

According to the UN, public administration has two closely related meanings:

First, an integrated state apparatus (policies, rules, procedures, systems, organizational structures, staff, etc.), which is financed from the state budget and is responsible for managing and coordinating the work of the executive branch, and its interaction with other stakeholders in the state, society and the external environment;

Secondly, the management and implementation of the whole set of state measures related to the implementation of laws, regulations and decisions of the government and management related to the provision of public services (*Bosak O.Z., 2010*).

Note that T. Kondratyuk defines public administration as a subsystem of the social system, a component of society, whose functioning and development are strongly influenced by all other spheres of public life (*Kondratyuk T.V., 2010*).

From this we can determine that public administration has key elements firstly, society, and secondly, public authority.

In the scientific literature we find two approaches to defining the concept of public administration.

In a broad sense, public administration is understood as the whole system of administrative institutions with a hierarchy of power, through which the responsibility for the implementation of state decisions goes from top to bottom. That is, public administration is a coordinated group action on public affairs, which: related to the three branches of government (legislative, executive and judicial; are important in shaping public policy; are part of the political process; significantly different from private sector administration; associated with numerous private groups and individuals working in different companies and communities.

In a narrow sense, public administration is related to the executive branch and is seen as: the professional activities of civil servants, which includes all activities aimed at implementing government decisions; study, development and implementation of government policy (*Meltyukhova N.M., 2010, p. 4*).

Thus, both public administration and public administration have both a broad and a narrow understanding and are very similar by the above definitions. However, public administration is an authoritarian type of government, and public administration is a democratic type of government.

Public administration is a close concept to public administration (governance) and some researchers even use them as synonyms. However, these terms are completely different.

Public administration is the link between government and public administration.

A number of scholars, including O. Bosak, M. Minenko, and Y. Surmin, consider public administration to be a transitional link or a stage from public administration to public governance.

O. Bosak notes that in the public sector the model of public administration ("bureaucratic model") has been transformed into a model of public administration ("market model") (*Bosak O.Z., 2010*).

Other scholars, including A. Kolodiy, V. Martynenko, Y. Sharov, define public administration as part of the management process, a component of public administration.

Professor Kolodiy A. argues that public administration is a kind of management of public authorities, through which the state and civil society ensure the self-government (self-government) of the entire social system and its development in a certain, defined direction (*Bazarna O.V. 20102, p. 489*).

V. Martynenko notes that public administration is a form of implementation of public administration, which is carried out by representative bodies of democratic governance through their executive structures (*Martynenko V.M., 2010, pp. 20-21*).

Let's turn to the etymology of words and analyze the pairs "state - public" and "management - administration". Of course, the concept of "public" is broader than "state" and includes such definitions as "state", and others: "public, popular, public, public, communal, open, public." That is, when using "public" in the field, we mean: what belongs to the executive branch, administrative apparatus, local government, public, belongs to the people.

As for "management", it includes "administration" and "management, ownership, leadership, organization".

Thus, public administration is a component of public administration (governance), the purpose of which is the development of the state on the basis of democracy using effective new methods and technologies of governance and aimed at providing citizens at the level of world standards.

Public administration is a set of state and non-state structures and authorized persons who carry out public governance and administration. Public administration includes executive bodies, the administrative apparatus and executive bodies of local self-government (*Democratic governance and public administration: problems of measurement and audit, 2011, p. 21*).

In public administration, the subject is public administration.

Conclusions and prospects for further research. Summing up, it should be noted that public administration and public administration are subtypes (components) of social management. Public administration is the link between public administration and public administration and ensures the organization and implementation of its decisions. The key elements for public administration are the state and state power, and for public administration - society and public power. In public administration, the object is the state, and in public administration, the object is society. Authoritarianism is characteristic of public administration, and democracy is characteristic of public administration. Thus, public administration introduces democratic values and contributes to the sustainable development of our state in the process of social transformation.

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